

ART AND EDUCATION

WHEN CHINESE CALLIGRAPHY SPEAKS: EXPLORING EMOTIONAL INTERPRETATION IN A SPANISH UNIVERSITY COMMUNITY

Cuando la caligrafía china habla: explorando la interpretación emocional en una comunidad universitaria española

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ABSTRACT

Background: In China, calligraphy has long been regarded not merely as a writing technique but as a manifestation of the calligrapher's personality and emotional states. The expression "calligraphy reflects the person", documented since the Han dynasty, has consolidated the idea that brushstrokes and writing styles project the calligrapher's inner world. However, this concept has received little scholarly attention in the Western context, where Chinese calligraphy is primarily valued as an artistic or pedagogical resource. **Objectives:** The aim of this study is to examine whether the emotional state of the calligrapher can be perceived by Western observers with no prior knowledge of the language or calligraphic practice. **Methodology:** To this end, an empirical investigation was conducted with 31 Spanish university students enrolled in the Degree in East Asian Studies at the University of Salamanca. None of the participants had training in Chinese calligraphy, and most were unfamiliar with the traditional characters used in the selected work. The material analyzed was *Draft of a Requiem to My Nephew* by Yan Zhenqing (709-785), an emblematic piece of the Tang dynasty and a notable example of semi-cursive script. Participants observed the work and completed a questionnaire consisting of closed-ended questions on the sensations perceived and open-ended questions on their interpretation of the calligrapher's emotional state. **Results:** Results show that 96.8% of participants identified predominantly negative emotions, mainly anger (67.7%) and anguish (19.4%). Although sadness was also part of the author's emotional background, only 3.2% recognized it. **Conclusion:** In conclusion, the findings reinforce the idea that calligraphy is a visual art capable of transmitting emotions perceptibly, even to non-Chinese-speaking observers. This study contributes to the intercultural understanding of calligraphic art and opens new avenues for exploring the relationship between art, emotion, and nonverbal communication.

KEY WORDS

Chinese Calligraphy, Emotional State, Empirical Research, Spanish University Students, Visual Art.

RESUMEN

Introducción: En China, la caligrafía ha sido considerada durante siglos no sólo como una técnica de escritura, sino como una manifestación de la personalidad y los estados emocionales del autor. La expresión "la caligrafía refleja a la persona", presente desde la dinastía Han, ha consolidado la idea de que los trazos y estilos de escritura son una proyección del mundo interior del calígrafo. Sin embargo, este concepto apenas ha sido explorado en el ámbito occidental, donde la caligrafía china se valora principalmente como recurso artístico o didáctico. **Objetivo:** El presente estudio tiene como objetivo analizar si el estado emocional del calígrafo puede ser percibido por observadores occidentales sin conocimiento previo de la lengua ni de la práctica caligráfica. **Metodología:** Para ello, se realizó una investigación empírica con 31 estudiantes universitarios españoles del Grado en Estudios de Asia Oriental de la Universidad de Salamanca. Ninguno de ellos tenía experiencia en caligrafía china y la mayoría desconocía los caracteres tradicionales utilizados en la obra seleccionada. El material de análisis fue *Borrador de un Réquiem para mi sobrino* de Yan Zhenqing (709-785), pieza emblemática de la dinastía Tang y ejemplo de caligrafía del estilo corriente. Los participantes observaron la obra y respondieron a un cuestionario con preguntas cerradas sobre las sensaciones percibidas y abiertas sobre la interpretación del estado emocional del calígrafo. **Resultados:** Los resultados muestran que el 96,8 % de los participantes identificaron emociones negativas predominantes, principalmente enfado (67,7 %) y angustia (19,4 %). Aunque la tristeza formaba parte del trasfondo emocional del autor, sólo un 3,2 % logró reconocerla. **Conclusión:** En conclusión, los hallazgos refuerzan la idea de que la caligrafía es un arte visual capaz de transmitir emociones de manera perceptible incluso a observadores no sinohablantes. Este trabajo contribuye a la comprensión intercultural del arte caligráfico y abre nuevas vías para explorar la relación entre arte, emoción y comunicación no verbal.

PALABRAS CLAVE

Caligrafía china, estado emocional, investigación empírica, universitarios españoles, arte visual.

INTRODUCTION

Chinese calligraphy is an ancient art deeply rooted in the culture and history of China since the Shang dynasty. The origins of calligraphy already forged links between the oracle bone script and courtly rituals, and it was highly valued by Confucian scholars due to its educational, political, and social role. Confucians considered calligraphy one of the Six Arts of a gentleman, and throughout the dynasties it became a crucial criterion for the selection of talents in the imperial examinations. Beyond its political and educational connections, calligraphy was an essential component of the spiritual and cultural life of scholars and officials in ancient China, serving as a medium to convey thoughts and expressions through distinctive visual forms (Chiang, 1974).

According to the renowned poet and calligrapher Su Shi (1037-1101), observing a person's calligraphy is the best way to truly know them. Su Shi's discourse embraces the timeless idea that judging appearances is misleading, whereas observing calligraphy is far more revealing. His view aligns with the saying "calligraphy reflects the person" (*shu ru qi ren* 书如其人), a concept of remote origin that traces back to the creation of Chinese characters, where inspiration was drawn from natural phenomena and combined with a holistic approach fusing the subjective and the objective (Liu, 2013). The original method of character creation was pictographic, early characters directly imitated the shapes of the objects they represented. This inherent pictographic quality allowed (and still allows) calligraphers to organically merge their personal style with the act of writing. Based on this tradition, Chen (2013) defines Chinese calligraphy as a four-dimensional art from a visual perspective. Moreover, ancient calligraphy rules were also linked to pictographic features. For example, Lady Wei (272-349), a renowned calligraphy master, summarized the positions of brushstrokes for her disciples using numerous comparisons and metaphors drawn from nature. In *Bizhen tu* 笔阵图 (compiled in 1980), one can find metaphors such as the horizontal stroke compared to a cloud stretching across the horizon, the dot stroke likened to a rock falling from a mountain, or the hook stroke compared to the shooting of a hundred arrows illustrating the strength and elasticity of the stroke.

Although the idea that calligraphy reflects a person has persisted throughout Chinese history, the expression itself first appeared in *Fa Yan* 法言 (The Fayan) by Yang Xiong (53 BCE-18 CE) during the Western Han dynasty (202 BCE-8 CE). According to Yang, calligraphy is "the painting of the heart", through calligraphy, one can perceive the noble

and the base, since calligraphy maintains an inner connection with the individual's character and serves as the outward manifestation of the soul (Duan, 2013; Jing, 2022). This external manifestation does not merely express the personality of the calligrapher but also reveals their emotional state.

Today, calligraphy continues to be highly valued in education, not only as a skill but also as a tool for enhancing concentration and fine motor coordination in students. At present, however, greater attention is given to hard calligraphy (writing with pen or pencil) than to soft calligraphy (writing with brush). Nevertheless, the concept that "calligraphy reflects the person" remains current in Chinese society, especially among primary school students, who devote substantial time and effort to its practice. Outside China, however, in the field of teaching Chinese as a foreign language, calligraphic writing is generally used only as a tool to learn characters or to stimulate interest in the language, as shown in studies by Sheng (2023) and Yang and Chi (2024). It is rarely approached as an art form for contemplation, independent of its pedagogical role. In fact, interviews with Spanish university students enrolled in the Degree in East Asian Studies at the University of Salamanca reveal a strong interest in learning about this millennia-old Chinese art, both theoretically and practically. This keen interest is what has motivated the present research, oriented toward these students.

Regarding studies on the concept that "calligraphy reflects the person," although some researchers focus on analyzing the relationship between calligraphy and emotional states, most research emphasizes the correlation between calligraphy and personality (Duan, 2013; Liu, 2013). Consequently, the aim of this study is to explore whether the notion that "calligraphy reflects the person" can also be confirmed among non-Chinese audiences, through their observation and perception of the emotions conveyed by calligraphers in their works, despite the language barrier.

The Relationship Between Calligraphy and Personality

Chinese calligraphy has long been regarded not only as an art form but also as a medium through which the personality of the calligrapher can be observed. This perspective is grounded in the idea that brushstrokes and writing style reflect the intrinsic characteristics of the writer.

The historical evolution of this concept can be traced back to the Western Han dynasty. Later, Liu Gongquan (778-865) of the Tang dynasty (681-907) expanded on Yang Xiong's ideas with

the theory of “a straight heart produces straight strokes” (*xin zheng ze bi zheng* 心正则笔正), suggesting that only a correct attitude could result in truly fine works, thereby achieving an organic unity between inner disposition and external form. In the Song dynasty (960-1279), the concept was promoted by Ouyang Xiu (1007-1072) and consolidated by Su Shi. The latter emphasized that all calligraphy reflects the person, such that one can distinguish between noble and base individuals by their writing. Appearances may be deceiving, but the moral disposition of the noble versus the base cannot be hidden, similarly, while some calligraphers may be skillful and others clumsy, the inner nature of the noble and the base remains unmistakable (Guo, 2020). Across the Yuan (1271-1368), Ming (1368-1644), and Qing (1636-1912) dynasties, this idea was further developed and refined, eventually forming a systematic body of thought through the work of Liu Xizai in the late Qing dynasty (Liu, 2013). After analyzing the style and spirit of calligraphers across different dynasties, Liu (1978) declared that calligraphy is like the person, like their talent, and like their ambition, in short, it simply mirrors the person themselves. This explanation may be seen both as a synthesis of the relationship between the creator and calligraphy in terms of form, spirit, and style, and as a theoretical generalization of the relationship between artistic personality and artistic style more broadly (Chen, 2013).

The connections between personality and calligraphy were thoroughly compiled by Chen Menglei (1650-1741) in his monumental *Gujin Tushu Jicheng* 古今图书集成 (*Complete Collection of Ancient and Modern Books*), published during the Qing dynasty. To illustrate the parallels between nature, personality, and calligraphy, Chen provided numerous examples:

If the style of characters is weak and solitary, like a white crane standing alone, it represents a poor and lonely person. If the characters are volatile and slippery, like flocks of crows in flight, they suggest a talkative person skilled with words. If the style is soft and disorderly, like a frightened snake without escape, it reflects someone merely seeking refuge. If the characters are agile and elegant, like the sacred crane leaving its nest, the person has great ambitions and determination. If the style is nervous and jumpy, like a magpie, the person is light and superficial. If the characters are calm and steady, like the pace of a goose, they reflect stability and tranquility. A dense design, like a bamboo grove, indicates an open and clear mind. A loose design, like the flow of water, suggests difficulties within the household. Rough characters,

like rocks, imply reliance on an adventurous life. Pointed characters, like jagged peaks, suggest independence and solitude. Uneven ink density and brightness reflect repeated frustrations in life. Misaligned character structures imply difficulties in everyday living (Chen, Qing dynasty).

To visualize these ideas, Figure 1 illustrates how calligraphy reveals personality in the works of two famous calligraphers in Chinese history. Ouyang Xun (557-641), who lived through many political rebellions, developed a prudent and cautious character that is reflected in his perfectly structured and firmly written calligraphy. In contrast, Chu Suiliang (596-658), born into a scholarly and powerful family, was trained by the greatest calligraphy masters of his time, acquiring the most advanced techniques. Although he was exiled in his later years, he spent much of his life in peace and glory, which shaped a more confident, cheerful, and proud character. Consequently, his writing is more vivid, dynamic, and fluid, conveying a strong sense of freedom. These differences highlight how the distinct personalities of the two calligraphers shaped their works, either rational and controlled or emotional and expressive.

Figure 1: Different Personalities Reflected in Calligraphy. Source: characters selected from Ouyang (2024) and Chu (2024).

Calligraphy as a Reflection of Emotional States

The concept that “calligraphy reflects the person” extends beyond personality, also encompassing the emotional state of the calligrapher at the moment of writing. Brushstrokes, rhythm, and applied pressure can all provide clues to underlying emotions. As Jing (2022) explains, calligraphy is an art that conveys the emotions of the writer through lines and ink. For instance, dry and trembling strokes may indicate

sadness, anxiety, or anger, since a lack of firmness suggests a shaking hand and a disturbed emotional state, resulting in writing that is less controlled and more inconsistent. In contrast, firm and clearly defined strokes often reflect positive emotions such as determination, confidence, and joy, because a stable and positive mindset enables precise control of the brush. The famous poet and calligrapher Su Shi, whose political life was marked by frustration, exemplifies this connection. His calligraphic works, particularly those created during his exile, reveal strokes that are more melancholic and reflective, mirroring his sadness and isolation.

When discussing the idea that calligraphy reflects emotional states, it is essential to mention the first renowned piece of semi-cursive script in Chinese calligraphy, the *Preface to the Orchid Pavilion Poems* by Wang Xizhi (303-361) of the Jin dynasty (266-420) (see Figure 2). The historical context of this masterpiece is that, in the year 353, Wang Xizhi gathered with 41 friends at the Orchid Pavilion. Amidst an atmosphere of joy, accompanied by wine and lively entertainment, the group composed poems. They then decided to compile the collection and invited Wang Xizhi to write the preface.

Figure 2: Preface to the Orchid Pavilion Poems.

Source: Wang (2016).

If one observes the work carefully, it becomes evident that it is divided into two parts. The first part (the right half of the piece) is written in a more orderly and unified manner, maintaining relatively consistent spacing between characters and lines. Additionally, the strokes are more clearly separated. In contrast, the second part (the left half of the piece) reveals abrupt changes, corrections and overwriting become more frequent, the spacing between characters varies, the lines lose their uniformity, and the strokes are mostly connected. This shift can be explained by the content. In the first half, Wang Xizhi narrates the setting and the convivial atmosphere with his friends, which results in a more joyful and relaxed calligraphy. The second half, however, takes a different tone as the calligrapher begins to reflect on life, becoming more emotional and uncertain in his wording. Coupled with the effects of wine, these reflections altered the appearance of the writing. This piece has been regarded as an unsurpassed masterpiece in the history of Chinese calligraphy. Wang Xizhi himself expressed great satisfaction with this version, attempting numerous times to rewrite the preface but never producing one that pleased him as much as the original. This underscores the importance that, in calligraphy,

as in other arts, the mental and emotional state of the artist holds at the moment of creation.

Furthermore, the relationship between calligraphy and psychology has been the focus of considerable research in recent years. Studies have explored how calligraphy can serve as a tool for psychological analysis and how it may contribute to emotional well-being. In some developed countries, this has even been recognized as graphology, a branch of psychology (Duan, 2013). Since ancient times, calligraphy has been considered an activity to strengthen the mind and induce bodily relaxation, and modern scientific studies have confirmed these benefits from an empirical perspective. Documented psychological effects include reductions in heart rate, blood pressure, and skin conductance; increases in skin temperature; slower breathing; and muscle relaxation. Calligraphic practice has also been shown to improve attention, emotional stability, and mental relaxation (Kao et al., 1989). Clinical studies further demonstrate the positive impact of calligraphy training in reducing anxiety levels among patients with anxiety disorders (Dong et al., 2006) and among cancer patients (Yang et al., 2010). In recent decades, the therapeutic application of calligraphy has

gained wide popularity, particularly in countries with long-standing calligraphic traditions such as China, Korea, and Japan.

METHODOLOGY

When people appreciate calligraphy, they often spontaneously reflect on the style and personality of the calligrapher (Chen, 2013), as well as on the emotional state expressed at the time of writing. As Zong (1981) defined, art is a technique, while ancient artists were themselves technicians, their work not only served practical purposes but also expressed life, individuality, and personality. With this in mind, and in order to determine whether the calligrapher's emotional state at the time of writing is reflected in the calligraphy and can be perceived by observers, an empirical study was conducted. The research employed a questionnaire designed to capture participants' impressions and sensations in response to a selected calligraphic work.

Selected Material

For this study, a semi-cursive script work by the great calligrapher Yan Zhenqing (709-785), *Draft of a Requiem to My Nephew* (see Figure 3), was

selected. The choice of a semi-cursive style piece was motivated by the following characteristics:

- Fluency and spontaneity, which allow the calligrapher to express emotions in a more direct and authentic way.
- Connection between strokes, creating a continuous flow of writing that reflects the calligrapher's mental state at the time of creation, with subtle variations in rhythm and pressure that may indicate different emotional states.
- Versatility and adaptability, enabling the flexible expression of a wide range of emotions, from calmness and serenity to excitement and agitation.
- Absence of strict formal rules typical of more traditional styles, granting the calligrapher greater freedom to manifest emotions.

Chiang (1974) and Kao, Xu and Kao (2021) also support this view. According to their studies, in comparison with other calligraphic styles, the semi-cursive script conveys emotions in a more direct and perceptible manner to observers, due to its capacity to capture subtle changes, as well as its dynamism and fluidity.

Figure 3: Draft of a Requiem to My Nephew.
Source: Yan (2016).

On the other hand, this work, created in the year 758, is regarded as the second most important piece of semi-cursive script in China and one of the most famous works by the Chinese calligrapher Yan Zhenqing, a prominent figure of the mid-Tang dynasty. Yan was a respected magistrate who played a significant role, together with his relatives, in the suppression of the An Lushan Rebellion (755-763). His entire family was admired for their integrity and loyalty, qualities that are powerfully reflected in his vigorous calligraphy. This piece was written in memory of his nephew, Yan Jiming, who died tragically during the suppression of the rebellion. Yan Jiming was executed after the city he defended fell into the hands of the rebels. The

work thus stands as a profoundly personal and painful tribute by Yan Zhenqing to his nephew. The emotional intensity of Yan Zhenqing is evident in the energetic and at times irregular strokes, which vividly convey his grief and anguish. As such, the piece is distinguished not only for its calligraphic value but also for its profound emotional depth. Each character is imbued with a strong emotional charge, made visible through variations in the thickness of strokes, the speed of execution, and the pressure of the brush. The intensity of his feelings, from sorrow to rage, is palpable in every line, offering a direct window into his mental state at the moment of writing. Finally, it should be noted that this piece was entirely unfamiliar to the study's participants.

Participants

A total of 31 participants took part in this study on a fully anonymous basis. All of them were university students enrolled in the elective course *Introduction to Chinese Calligraphy: History, Theory, and Practice*, offered in the third and fourth years of the Degree in East Asian Studies at the University of Salamanca. Among the participants, 8 were male (25.8%) and 23 were female (74.2%). Not all of them had prior knowledge of the Chinese language. Those studying Chinese had only learned simplified characters, while the calligraphic works used in this research were written in traditional characters. None of the participants had previously studied Chinese calligraphy, and therefore they were unable to understand either the characters or the textual content of the selected work. Before participating in this study, they had only received

a basic introduction consisting of seven hours of theoretical instruction on Chinese calligraphy and seven hours of practical training in writing.

Procedure

The participants first observed the calligraphic work. They were then given ten minutes to complete a questionnaire that included demographic questions, as well as a closed-ended item asking them to identify the main sensation conveyed by the piece, choosing from options such as calmness, anger, sadness, anguish, joy, relaxation, among others. In addition, the questionnaire included an open-ended question in which participants were asked to describe in detail what they thought the text might say, what it was attempting to express, and any possible emotional changes in the calligrapher, based on their observation and/or imagination.

RESULTS

The Sensation Conveyed by Draft of a Requiem to My Nephew

Table 1: Results of Perceived Sensations.

Negative Sensations		Frequency	Percentage	Positive Sensations	Frequency	Percentage
Anger		21	67.7%	Calmness	0	0.0%
Sadness		1	3.2%	Joy	0	0.0%
Anguish		6	19.4%	Relaxation	0	0.0%
Others	Frustration	2	6.5%	Spontaneity	1	3.2%
Total		30	96.8%		1	3.2%

According to the results shown in Table 1, it is evident that merely by observing the piece, without understanding its textual content, almost all participants (96.8%) were able to perceive that the emotions conveyed by the calligrapher were predominantly negative. Among them, the majority reported a sensation of anger (67.7%), while another six participants (19.4%) perceived the anguish expressed by the calligrapher through his work. However, when Yan Zhenqing wrote this piece, in addition to being filled with anger at betrayal and the cruelty of people during the rebellion, he was also overwhelmed with sorrow at the death of his young and promising nephew. Yet this latter aspect was only identified by one participant (3.2%).

Observations on the Work

As illustrated in Figure 4, the participants' responses to the open-ended question, asking them to describe in detail what they believed was written, what the piece was attempting to express, and any possible emotional changes of the calligrapher, were based on their observation and/or imagination. In all cases, participants went beyond simply describing the visual features of

the work, attempting instead to correlate these characteristics with the potential emotional state of the calligrapher.

With regard to the features of this piece, one of the first elements that stands out is the presence of numerous corrections and erasures, which appear not to be intended to modify or refine the written strokes but rather to achieve more precise expressions. Another evident feature is the abundance of dry brushstrokes. Psychologically, this dry sensation is often difficult to tolerate, leading most writers to apply more ink. However, in this piece, the calligrapher's attention was not on the ink itself, allowing the strong friction between brush and paper to be felt, thereby creating a unique and distinctive texture. The question of ink density, its abundance or scarcity, is a complex concept and one that may easily go unnoticed, particularly for participants lacking knowledge of both the Chinese language and Chinese history. Although Yan Zhenqing was immersed in profound grief while composing this work, he still preserved his loyalty to the emperor. This is evident in the eighteenth line (counting from the right), where, upon mentioning the emperor, he left the

previous line unfinished and began a new one, so that the emperor's name could be placed at the top of the piece. At the same time, numerous firm strokes can also be observed, written with considerable pressure and force. These features reveal a shift in the calligrapher's work from aesthetics to practicality, where the form of the writing becomes less important than its utility and

content, prevailing over the sublimation of beauty.

Among these characteristics, participants primarily noted the corrections and erasures, the changes in writing rhythm, and the variations in brush pressure, which resulted in strokes of differing thicknesses. However, the evident feature of dry brushstrokes was mentioned by only one participant.

Figure 4: Observation of Writing Characteristics Related to Emotional State.

With regard to the emotional state perceived, the findings were consistent with the earlier results. Almost all participants indicated that they sensed the calligrapher's anger while writing the piece, and some even described it as a loss of emotional control. Many participants also noted changes in the calligrapher's state, emphasizing that he appeared calmer at the beginning but gradually lost control of his emotions, becoming increasingly carried away by anger and fury.

In terms of the relationship between writing features and emotional states, participants identified the expressive force of the work primarily through the corrections and erasures, which were interpreted as evidence of the calligrapher's agitation. These were followed by rapid brush movements and firm strokes executed with considerable pressure, both of which conveyed his emotional intensity. Other key indicators were the changes in writing rhythm, the corrections, and the variations in brush

pressure. When the author appeared calmer, he wrote more slowly, with better control of brush pressure, producing strokes that were more secure and precise; as a result, fewer corrections were needed. By contrast, as his state gradually shifted toward anger, he wrote more quickly and spent less time choosing words or organizing the text, which led to a higher frequency of corrections. Beyond aesthetics, to express his fury and rage, the calligrapher pressed the brush more forcefully against the paper, releasing his inner turmoil and attempting to give vent to his emotions. However, one participant interpreted this variation in stroke thickness not as emotional expression, but as a deliberate technique to highlight the content, in other words, the intention may have been to emphasize certain passages of the text rather than to reveal his emotions.

In addition, eight participants (25.8%) ventured to speculate on the historical background of

the piece. Two suggested that the changes and disorderly writing were primarily the result of alcohol consumption, while others believed that the calligrapher was expressing frustration with a particular situation, engaged in an argument, or concerned about the suffering of the people during wartime. The latter interpretation was, quite surprisingly, very close to the actual historical context of the piece.

DISCUSSION

This study explored the relationship between Chinese calligraphy and the calligrapher's emotional state, as well as the ability of Western observers with little prior knowledge of calligraphy or the Chinese language to infer such emotions from the writing itself. The results reinforce the notion that calligraphy is not only a visual art but also a manifestation of the writer's inner state.

With respect to the connection between calligraphy and emotion, the findings of this research indicate that strokes and writing styles can vary significantly depending on the calligrapher's emotional state. The presence of corrections, erasures, changes in rhythm, arrangement, and brush pressure were key indicators used by participants to infer emotions such as calmness or anger. This suggests a perceptible correlation between the quality and character of the writing and the calligrapher's emotional condition at the time of creation. These results are consistent with the theory of Liu (1978) from the Qing dynasty, who argued that calligraphy is a direct reflection of the person, encompassing their talent, ambition, and emotional state. The historical evolution of this idea, from the Han to the Qing dynasties, demonstrates a gradual acceptance and consolidation of the concept that calligraphy can serve as a window into the calligrapher's soul.

Regarding interpretation by observers, in this case, university students of East Asian Studies at the University of Salamanca, their ability to correctly infer the calligrapher's emotional state varied. Nonetheless, the great majority of participants (96.8%) were able to identify key signs indicating emotional changes. Almost all could distinguish between negative and positive states, using cues such as the firmness of brushstrokes and the presence of corrections. Some participants, however, attributed certain aspects to other factors, such as the calligrapher's intention to emphasize content. This highlights the dependence of calligraphy on visual signals, which cannot in themselves convey contextual knowledge or align with the observers' emotional sensitivity. The findings suggest that while some indicators

are universal, others may be subjective, shaped by the experiences and perceptions of individual observers. Despite this complexity, participants were still able to achieve a high degree of accuracy in recognizing the emotions conveyed by the calligrapher and even to identify changes in the author's feelings during the act of writing. For example, interpretations of stroke intensity may vary depending on whether the observer has experience analyzing art or possesses particular sensitivity to stylistic variations. Nevertheless, even without in-depth knowledge of Chinese calligraphy, observers were able to make meaningful inferences about the calligrapher's emotional state, underscoring the universal nature of certain aspects of emotional expression in art.

It must be acknowledged, however, that this study has limitations. It focused on a specific group of non-Chinese-speaking observers and employed a very limited number of calligraphic samples, which may constrain the generalizability of the results. Furthermore, the participants' unfamiliarity with Chinese calligraphy and the language may have influenced their ability to accurately interpret certain details.

CONCLUSIONS

The present study demonstrates that Chinese calligraphy is a manifestation of the calligrapher's emotional state, observable through variations in strokes and writing styles. Despite their lack of prior knowledge of calligraphy or the Chinese language, participants were able to infer emotions such as calmness and anger based on specific visual cues. This reinforces the idea that calligraphy can serve as a window into the writer's inner world.

These findings not only corroborate historical theories regarding the relationship between calligraphy and personality but also highlight the significance of calligraphy as a medium of emotional expression. By observing details such as the firmness of brushstrokes and the presence of corrections, even observers without prior knowledge can discern aspects of the calligrapher's emotional state.

Finally, this study underscores the need for further research into this fascinating connection between art and emotion, extending the exploration of calligraphy to other groups of observers and cultural contexts. A deeper understanding of how calligraphy reflects emotional states can enrich both the appreciation of art and the comprehension of nonverbal communication.

In conclusion, Chinese calligraphy is not merely

a means of written communication but a rich art form that profoundly reflects the emotional fluctuations of the calligrapher. This study provides a solid foundation for future explorations at the intersection of art and emotion and highlights the enduring relevance and beauty of calligraphy in the modern world.

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